

ВИДЕО КАК ДИДАКТИЧЕСКИЙ РЕСУРС И СТРАТЕГИЯ В ИЗУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА В ЧАСТНОМ ВУЗЕ

**Норбоева Феруза Рахматуллаевна, Заведующая кафедрой Языков
Ташкентского университета, прикладных наук, доцент, кандидат
педагогических наук**

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы, связанные с использованием мультимедийных материалов на уроках английского языка в частном вузе.

Ключевые слова: информационные технологии, образовательный процесс, методика, цифровые платформы, интернет-порталы, иностранный язык, обучающее видео.

XUSUSIY OLIY TA'LIMDA UNGLIZ TILINI O'QITISHDA VIDEO DIDAKTIK RESURS VA STRATEGIYA SIFATIDA

**Norboyeva Feruza Raxmatullayevna, TAFU Tillar kafedراس mudiri,
pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.**

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola xususiy oliy ta'lim maskanlarida ingliz tili darslarida multimedia materiallaridan foydalanish bilan bog'liq masalalarni ko'rib chiqadi.

Kalit so'zlar: axborot texnologiyalari, o'quv jarayoni, metodologiya, raqamli platformalar, internet portallar, chet tili, o'quv videosi.

VIDEO AS A DIDACTIC RESOURCE AND STRATEGY IN STUDYING ENGLISH IN A PRIVATE UNIVERSITY

**Norboeva Feruza Rakhmatullaevna, Head of the Department of
Languages, Tashkent University, Applied Sciences, Associate Professor,
candidate of pedagogical sciences.**

ANNOTATION

This article deals with issues related to the use of multimedia materials in English lessons in a private university.

Key words: information technology, educational process, methodology, digital platforms, Internet portals, foreign language, training video.

With the advent of information technologies and their use in the educational process, there is a need to development of methods of using such multimedia as images (drawings), presentations, cartoons, video interview, video report, video clip and the like. Today, the method of working with video materials in connection with the wide use of digital platforms, applications, set tools that allow working with audiovisual materials. There are no video materials homogeneous in view of their didactic use: educational video, the didactic purpose of which is preliminary

was formulated, and a professional video, the purpose of which is not only didactic in nature, but also pure informative from a certain field of human activity (we are talking about specialized Internet portals). Goal didactic video - to contribute to the dissemination of new knowledge and their assimilation, to be a motivator for the student obtaining new knowledge, thanks to the combination of image and sound, which contributes to the activation of various types memory (motor, emotional, figurative, verbal-logical, which are necessary for mental activity in various types activities of the linguistic personality; arbitrary - arbitrary depending on the purpose of the activity; short term, long-term and operative to preserve knowledge). Audiovisual communication serves to develop skills understanding of the natural flow of speech in a foreign language in imagined communicative situations combined with the norms of national and cultural behavior of speakers whose language is studied as a foreign language.

The use of video as didactic material performs the following functions in the formation of one's own vision a student of the surrounding world of speakers of the language he is studying, as well as the national specificity of the language society, in in which a foreign language functions:

- informative: obtaining new knowledge;

- motivational: the desire of the student to obtain new knowledge;
- expressive: the student's reaction to the content of the video;
- evaluative: positive or negative attitude towards the content of the video;
- research: implementation of research work by a student;
- metalinguistic: accentuation of the student's attention to the code/s themselves;
- entertaining, playful: development of language and thinking as a whole;
- interactive: student and teacher interaction; a combination of all the above functions.

Video combines elements of other multimedia, such as photography, frame, text, sound, i.e an educational video is a means of communication that has its own language/code, a sequence of its structures encourages the addressee to generalize feelings, thoughts, concepts, etc., which allows to expand knowledge, accumulated earlier.

Video as a multi-sensory communication is based on audiovisual language, sound, images.

Characteristics of audiovisual language:

- mixed communication system (visual and audio);
- is based on the worldwide experience of combining visual and audiovisual information;
- elements of this language have a certain meaning only in case of a certain sequence in their entirety totality;
- reaction often precedes comprehension through affective stimuli that generate cognitive structures.

The following types of videos are distinguished:

- educational: they are directly used in the educational process when studying/teaching a specific subject or topic;
- cultural: dedicated to the culture of a certain country, to various types of art, cultural and artistic events, etc.;
- scientific: reflect the process and results of scientific research;

- educational: interpreted as an educational strategy and didactic resource

A distinction should be made between educational video and the use of video for educational purposes. The training video is this a didactic resource and at the same time a didactic strategy aimed at improving the process learning/teaching a foreign language both online and offline. Importance of application educational video series in the educational process is based on scientific developments of well-known psychologists Piaget J. [2]), Vygotsky L.S. [1]), This is also confirmed by the semiological theory of Umberto Eco [3, 4]), when a scientist talks about the fact that the image becomes a means that is aimed at education.

Types of educational videos:

- video classes: used in distance learning, they are identical in structure to offline occupation and aimed at assimilating new knowledge, developing skills for the future professional activities;
- reference video: thematic video that the teacher uses in a lecture, seminar, practical session with foreign language;
- interactive videos: the teacher acts as a moderator, encourages students to immerse themselves in the material, which is studied;
- educational package: this is a selection of materials by topic for independent or remote work teaching; it includes test materials; audio text accompanied by pictures, photos, ie a kind of iconic text; methodical handbooks; short video films, usually thematic; educational programs; Software.

Given that video is a combination of different symbol systems (as already mentioned, text-sound image), it is a real representation of events in the corresponding space and time. According to some foreign methodologists [5], educational video is largely more artificial, unlike other types video due to the fact that it focuses too much on the pronunciation of sounds and intonation, as well as on non-verbal factors speech communication. Despite this, the educational videos are aimed at the cognitive needs of the student/s.

From the above follows a number of strategies aimed at creating new educational technologies, adaptation of the student to the foreign language

environment through the construction and assimilation of cognitive structures, immersion in a foreign-language culture, assimilation of the speech-specific norms of a foreign-language society:

- instructional strategy: students' focus on assimilation of new knowledge;
- cognitive strategy: expanding knowledge on the subject being studied;
- motivational strategy: orientation of the student towards acquiring new knowledge;
- modeling strategy: reproduction of a certain fragment of reality in speech based on representations of this fragment using concepts, conceptual structures, their schemes and models, inherent in the foreign language being studied;
- game strategy: speech actions in various speech situations;
- emotional and expressive strategy: study and reproduction of the expressive component of speech behavior.

Thanks to different genres of video (short and full-length, documentaries, interactive games, music videos, video blogs, presentations, interviews, colloquiums, etc.), the student learns the language not only as system of codes, but also the entire range of support for the implementation of language in speech: the communicative situation in its specific presentation (intonation, body language, gestures, reactions, i.e. non-verbal factors which accompany live communication in any language). If the language feature when communicating is native language does not focus on extra-linguistic factors of speech communication, but automatically uses them, then when communicating in a foreign language, a non-native speaker must be familiar with peculiarities of the national and cultural behavior of the language society whose language is being studied. It's a series of videos contributes to the foreigner's immersion in speech behavior. The video conveys real conditions of communication and even helps to understand the texts read (it is appropriate to note that the Internet texts are real, not artificial, as in many textbooks). In addition, the student is able to interact on various forums to exchange opinions about the content of the video (we will also add the read text) with language features another language society.

Literature:

1. **Выготской Л.С.** Мышление и речь: монография/ Л.С. Выготский – М.: Директ-Медиа, 2014, 570 стр.
2. **Пиаже Ж.** Психология интеллекта URL:
<https://biblioclub.ru/index.php?page=book&id=39214>
3. **Эко У.** Введение в семиологию. URL:
<http://www.philol.msu.ru/~discours/images/stories/speckurs/eco-lastrutturaassente.pdf>
4. **Есо U.** Apocalípticos e integrados ante la cultura de masas. URL:
https://monoskop.org/images/c/c4/Eco_Umberto_Apocalipticos_E_Integrados_1984.pdf
5. **Ventus D.R., Romeo G.N.** El uso del video en la enseñanza del inglés como lengua extranjera. URL:
<http://www.mextesol.net/journal/public/files/9212486a1750d92070781e5f413989.pdf>